

STRUCTURED MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES FOR POWER STORAGE DEVICES

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SUMMARY

We report the fabrication and performance of multifunctional composite materials for energy storage application. The electrochemical and mechanical properties of the obtained composites were systematically studied.

Keywords: multifunctional materials, energy storage device, supercapacitor, polymer electrolyte, electrical and mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

The focus of the research presented here relates to the relatively new and developing area of multifunctional composite materials. The advantage of multifunctional composite materials is that they can simultaneously carry out two or more functions. In case of multifunctional composites for energy storage devices, mechanical and electrical properties have to be considered. Use of such material together or as an alternative for conventional energy storage systems would reduce weight of the final product, improve redundancy or enhance performance. The laminated architecture of fibre composites mirrors the configuration of many current electrical storage devices. In fact, carbon fibre (CF) composites are attractive as they are commonly used as both electrodes and high performance structural reinforcements [1-4]. The variety of the carbon forms provides an opportunity to unify these roles with appropriate tailoring of both the matrix and the reinforcement.

Achievements in polymer development allow to use them as structural matrix and as an electrolyte [5-8]. Using polymers in both roles simultaneously would be possible when polymers can provide mechanical support to reinforcing fibres without compromising the electrochemical performance.

Compared with liquid electrolytes, solid state (gel) polymer electrolytes provide increased durability and reduced leakage of electrolyte; in addition, they are relatively cheap, easy to prepare, and have a wide voltage window. On the other hand, the disadvantage of polymer electrolytes is their relatively low ionic conductivity; using organic plasticizers (such as propylene carbonate, ethylene carbonate) to swell the polymer matrix leads to improvements in electrochemical performance by allowing greater mobility of the ions.

The addition of discrete inorganic particles such as SiO₂, Al₂O₃, TiO₂ into polymer electrolytes is known as an effective means of improving both conductivity and

mechanical properties [9, 10]. The resulting ionic conductivity can be good (up to 0.001 S/cm) [9, 11] but, despite improvements, the absolute mechanical properties are still quite poor (tensile strength typically only up to 2.5 MPa) [9].

The reported system, based on carbon fibres, glass fibre and poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether, contains mesoporous silica structure which provides continuous phase for ionic conductivity and mechanical robustness. Furthermore, this system intrinsically can not exhibit phase separation effects due to formation of two interpenetrated networks; polymer (cross linked poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether) and mesoporous silica, thus the device variability and failure associated with agglomeration or poor distribution of the silica are avoided.

EXPERIMENT

PAN-based woven (five harness satin weave) HTA carbon fibre cloths, with an areal density 200 gm⁻² and a thickness of the woven mat of 0.27 mm kindly supplied by Tissa Glasweberei AG (Oberkulm, Switzerland) were used as electrode material for composites in this work. The glass fibre (GF) woven 6K (twill weave) cloth with areal density 250 gm⁻² and thickness of the woven mat of 0.24 mm was also kindly provided by Tissa Glasweberei AG (Oberkulm, Switzerland).

Pluronic 123 ((EO)₂₀(PO)₇₀(EO)₂₀) (poly(ethylene oxide)-poly(propylene oxide)-poly(ethylene oxide) block copolymers) was kindly supplied by BASF Corporation (Florham Park, New Jersey, U.S.A.). Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS >99%) was obtained from Fluka, propylene carbonate (PC) (HPLC grade), tetrabutyl ammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆) (battery grade) was obtained from Sigma and poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether (PEGDGE) (M_n =526) from Aldrich, triethylenetetraamine (TEtA) was kindly provided by CIBA (Basel, Switzerland). All other chemicals were used as received.

Preparation of Ion Conducting Polymer Matrix

TBAPF₆ was dissolved in PC and after that PEGDGE was added. After that the system was mixed until a homogenous solution was obtained. Then TEtA was added to PEGDGE and the mixture kept at 80°C until the viscosity of the solution started to increase (about 30 min).

Composite Fabrication

Composites for Electrochemical Characterization

Impregnation of the carbon fibres fabrics for PEGDGE polymer electrolytes: the carbon fibre and glass fibre fabric were impregnated manually with the polymer electrolyte from both sides using an artist brush Number 10 and the composite was laid up by hand ensuring that the lay-up was balanced (*i.e.* the crimp lines of the CF plies were mirrored about the mid-plane). The samples were then kept overnight at 80°C under light applied pressure allowing enough time for PEGDGE cross-linking.

MPS based composite filled with PEGDGE electrolytes for electrochemical and mechanical characterisation was prepared using the following procedure: two carbon fibre mats, with a glass fibre mat in between, were placed into a mould and the MPS reaction mixture containing a solution of Pluronic 123 and TEOS was poured over the fibres. The synthesis of silica was carried out at acidic pH via sol gel process using Pluronic 123 as a template. The mould containing the fibres and reaction mixture was then held at 14°C until the mixture solidified. Then the template was removed and the

composite was dried in the vacuum oven overnight at 70°C, followed by the filling composite with electrolyte.

All laminates for mechanical tests were fabricated using an RIFT infusion route.

Electrochemical Analysis of Carbon Fibres and Composites

The specific capacitance was calculated from the maximum cyclic voltammetric current cyclic voltammogram at 0.1V divided by the scan rate.

The charge-discharge experiments for the composites were performed at room temperature using a 0.1 V step voltage applied for 10 s. The capacitance (C , F) was calculated using $C = I\Delta t/\Delta V$, where I is the discharge current (A) and Δt is the time period for the voltage change (ΔV). The specific capacitance was calculated as capacitance per unit weight (F/g).

Cyclic voltammetry tests for the composites were conducted at room temperature using sweep rates of 5 mV/s to 50 mV/s within a voltage window of -0.5 to 0.5 V. This voltage window was selected to avoid water decomposition. The capacitance was calculated using the equation $C = (I \times t)/V$, where I is the discharge current density, t is the time of discharge.

The electrochemical impedance of the supercapacitors was determined using a Solartron 1260 impedance/gain-phase analyzer coupled with Solartron 1255B Frequency Response Analyser (Farnborough, Hampshire, U.K.). The measurements were conducted at room temperature in a frequency range from 10^6 Hz to 10^{-3} Hz and sinusoidal voltage amplitude of 5 mV.

Mechanical Characterisation of the Structural Composites Supercapacitor Prototypes

The compressive stiffness and strength in the weft (90°) direction of the composites were determined using ASTM Standard D5467 [12]. The compression performance was chosen in this study because this mechanical property is considered to be one of the critical parameters for design and is known to be dictated by the shear stiffness and strength of the matrix [13]. The low thickness of the laminates in this study meant conventional compression methods [14] could not be utilised to characterise these materials. Therefore, the mechanical properties were characterised using sandwich beams under four point bending to induce a membrane compressive stress in the composite face. The sandwich consisted of 20 mm thick aluminium honeycomb core and the composite laminate face sheet.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We report the fabrication and performance of composite materials based on carbon fibres and polymer gel electrolytes reinforced glass fibres. Poly(ethylene glycol) diclycidyl ether was chosen as the base for the polymer gel electrolyte because its molecular composition. Polyethylene glycol, part of the matrix, is widely used in polymer gel electrolyte formulations due to its high solvation capability for salts. Existence of epoxy groups in the PEGDGE allows to control mechanical performance of electrolyte by changing the cross linking density.

The electrochemical performance of the composites was examined using impedance spectroscopy, cyclic voltammetry and charge-discharge measurements. A typical Nyquist plot for composites impregnated by PEGDGE presented in Figure 1 and can be broadly divided into two regions in all cases. At high frequencies, the capacitive impedance Z'' ($= -1/\omega C$) is small, but rises as the frequency diminishes. There is a semicircular shape associated with a parallel combination of capacitive and resistive

components, relating to the parallel plate geometry and net current leakage/ionic resistance, respectively.

At lower frequencies, the electrochemical charging of the double layer surface becomes significant, as ions have time to move to the electrodes. The change in behaviour is evident at a critical “knee frequency” that defines the maximum operating frequency at which the majority of the electrochemical capacitance can be obtained. The values for the “knee frequency” in the impedance measurements correlate with the results from the charge-discharge experiments, discussed below (Table 1). At higher frequencies, the capacitance begins to decrease and is strongly frequency dependant, so in practical applications the device should be operated below this value. In the low frequency regime the impedance response approaches a vertical, purely capacitive response for studied systems.

Figure 1 . Nyquist plot for CF reinforced PEGDGE electrolyte composites containing TBAPF₆, LiPF₆, LiClO₄.

Three different salt were used in the carbon fibre composites reinforced PEGDGE. As mentioned above a semicircle was observed for all studied composites at high frequency range followed by a straight line in the low frequency range (Fig. 1). The smallest semicircle and the internal resistance among the studied systems was observed for the composite containing TBAPF₆ which corresponded to the lowest impedance at the electrode/electrolyte interface (Table 1).

It was also found that the composite containing TBAPF₆ showed better charge-discharge capability and lower leakage value compared to the other composites. While the composite containing LiPF₆ showed the poorest charge-discharge capability with the smallest value of specific capacitance (Table 1). However, there is an obvious leakage current underlying the exponential capacitive charging current. The leakage current can be estimated from the final charging current after the capacitive component dies away, or from the difference between charging and discharging capacity of the composite. The data for leakage current presented in the Table 1 were calculated using the latter method.

Table 1. Discharging capability and specific capacitance for carbon fibre reinforced PEGDGE electrolyte composites containing different salts.

Sample description	Charge-discharge			Impedance measurement			Cyclic voltammetry $C_g \cdot 10^3$ (F/g)
	Discharge $\cdot 10^3$ (C)	Δ^b (%)	$C_g \cdot 10^3$ (F/g)	$C_g \cdot 10^3$ (F/g)	Knee frequency (Hz)	R^c (Ω)	
TBAPF ₆	0.22	39.4	0.27	0.13	200	520	0.27
LiPF ₆	0.092	47.6	0.14	0.11	79	790	0.15
LiClO ₄	0.15	49.5	0.21	0.086	160	660	0.21

^a difference between charging and discharging capability of the sample in Coulomb or ^b percentage difference between charging and discharging capability of the composite divided by charging capability; ^c R is the internal resistance of the electrodes (low intercept with Z').

The performance of the composites was checked at different times after the preparation of the composites. It is clear from Fig. 2 that the major changes took place in first 4 days. The better performance in the first hour could be due to the composite preparation procedure. The setting of the PEGDGE usually take several hours, so, during first couple of hours the electrolyte is gel-like should allow for higher ion-diffusion compare to crosslinked PEGDGE.

Figure 2. Nyquist plot for CF reinforced PEGDGE electrolyte composites with TBAPF₆. The measurements were done in (a) 1 h; (b) 4 days; (c) 2 weeks after preparation of the composites.

According to the data obtained from the impedance spectroscopy and charging-discharging method it can be concluded that no significant changes happened during composite storage (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of the storage time on the performance of for carbon fibres reinforced PEGDGE electrolyte composites

Storage time	Charge-discharge			Impedance measurement	
	Discharge $\cdot 10^3$, C	Δ^a , %	$C_g \cdot 10^3$, F/g	$C_g \cdot 10^3$, F/g	R , ^b Ω
1 h	0.29	32.0	0.37	0.23	480
4 days	0.22	34.0	0.27	0.19	540
2 weeks	0.22	39.4	0.27	0.13	520

^a percentage difference between charging and discharging capability of the composite divided by charging capability; ^b R is the internal resistance of the electrodes (low intercept with Z')

The results of the mechanical characterisation using the four bending tests are presented in Table 2. It was found that the MPS structure alone performs sufficiently well mechanically, confirming the effectiveness of the nano-structured matrix strategy. However, comparing the infused composites with the control laminate (Baseline) shows that the introduction of the MPS phase led to a 28% drop in stiffness which can be attributed to incomplete resin infiltration or poor interfacial adhesion between carbon fibres and resin filled MPS. However, no significant changes in the mechanical performance were observed for the composites containing the MPS phase regardless of the resins to fill the MPS. However, the strength of all the silica reinforced laminates was very poor, ranging between 13% and 22% of the control laminate value (Table 3). It was apparent during testing, that failure was associated with delamination of the layers, suggesting again poor infiltration or poor adhesion between carbon fibres and resin.

The typical stress/strain behaviour up to non-linearity of the laminates is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Stress/strain behaviour of prototypes of structural composite supercapacitor.

The basic concept of a multifunctional material has been demonstrated but it still needs considerable further development. A new matrix system which provides electrolyte function whilst supporting mechanical load was introduced. It was shown that the

introduction of a nano-structured, mesoporous silica reinforcing phase has the potential to allow the matrix to successfully perform both roles simultaneously. Clearly, further optimization is required to optimize the scale of the pore structure and to improve the interfacial interactions that control strength and interfacial performance.

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